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Fratelli-Sorelle Tutti: **A Call to Live Our Faith** **with Hope and Joy**

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Abstract: *Fratelli-Sorelle Tutti* appeals to all people of good will. The values of love and care are embedded in every human person. Catholics caught up in an individualistic faith practice and secure in their parish Church, have been called by Pope Francis to Synodality through communion, participation and mission. He calls us to look beyond ourselves, beyond the walls of our home, our parish, to the larger world, the reality of the poor, the violence done to women, to the abuse of human rights, peoples of other faiths, etc. to create a culture of encounter, towards fraternity and communion as one human family. We need a new culture to bring about change, where feminist perspectives are included

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to address the problems of society, business, politics and the environment. It is essential to get the youth on board in the process of working towards synodality as they would resonate with *Fratelli-Sorelle Tutti*.

Keywords: Love, Communion, Fraternity, Human Family, Human Rights, Encounter, Justice.

1. Fratelli-Sorelle Tutti Is Universal

Fratelli/Sorelle Tutti is based on the fundamental concept that all humans are created equal by God, and therefore is a sister or brother who needs to be acknowledged and treated as such. It appeals to all people of good will who seek justice and peace. Love and care are values deeply embedded in each and every human that need to be affirmed and nurtured.

Having been part of the women's movement in India for the past 30 years, I have been heartened to see how women of all faiths or no faith, have dedicated their lives to work for justice not only for women but also for people of the lower castes who suffer discrimination. I have observed that 'fraternity' and 'social relations' that this document is dedicated to, is integral to the women's movement in India.

For example, in 1992 when Bhanwari Devi, a grassroots social worker in Rajasthan was gang raped by upper caste men to take revenge for her efforts to prevent a child marriage in their family, women's organizations in Rajasthan immediately were on the alert and followed the shoddy way the case was handled by the local police and lower courts. When the accused were acquitted in 1995, they put pressure on the Rajasthan government to appeal against the judgement in the case. The government dragged their feet but finally did so in 2007 when 2 of the accused had died. From that case the women activists were able to draft a law on Sexual harassment of women in the workplace that helps numerous women who suffer this indignity and violence in their workplaces.

Medha Patkar (Wikipedia contributors 2021) is another woman who has incarnated herself into the lives of those displaced by the Narmada dam project in Madhya Pradesh and Gujarat. Since the mid-1980s to this day she has dedicated her life to work for their rehabilitation and right to livelihood. Born into a family of socially conscious parents, she grew up to be sensitive to the sufferings and needs of the voiceless in Indian society. She gave the displaced people hope and courage to continue their struggle against an insensitive government.

Flavia Agnes, as a young wife and mother experienced very serious domestic violence. She found solace and hope in the women's movement. As a Catholic she did not find much support in the Church, except for some priests who gave her a listening ear but directed her to the movement. She was finally able to leave her violent husband when she was given shelter in the home of a Hindu activist, the late Sonal Shukla. Sonal not only opened her home and hearth to Flavia and her children, she even gave her clothes to wear, and helped her pick up the threads of her life again. Today Flavia is a noted Advocate, thanks to the encouragement of Sonal. Flavia fights for women's rights and takes up cases of violence against women. Sonal, a Hindu woman lived "*Sorelle Tutti*", she was Eucharist to Flavia and her children at a low point in their life.

The movement consists of women who are lawyers, activists, social workers, etc., who are willing to walk that extra mile to go to the aid of any woman or child that has suffered violence. They put their lives out for the sake of another. The sisterhood is amazing. This is how we should be living the Eucharist moved by the Spirit of God.

While we also have several religious and even some lay women and men who have "walked alongside the poor, the abandoned, the infirm and the outcast, the least of their

brothers and sisters” (FT 2) the majority of Catholics are content with being ‘consumers of church services’, completely absorbed in following the commandments of the Church; satisfied with membership in some pious association, feeling satisfied that we are ‘practising’ Catholics. Even though Jesus has clearly said “Not everyone who says to me “Lord, Lord” will enter the kingdom of heaven, but the one who does the will of God (Matt.7:21), we still tend to assure our place in heaven by the number of masses we attend, the number of rosaries we say, novenas, etc. We even have people being proclaimed as a “good Catholic” for being seen around the Church a lot, being involved in parish activities which are mainly inward looking.

When I was a very young widow with three infant children, I struggled to go through each day. Another widow who had been through a similar experience came a month later and told me that I could leave my children at her home if I needed to go out on work. Most other people’s concern was more intrusive than helpful.

2. Are We Truly Living Our Faith?

Pope Francis in calling on all the People of God to Synodality through Communion, Participation and Mission is trying to reform the way we practice our faith. There is no doubt that the way we have been practising our faith has left us all in a rut of individualism because we have grown up on doctrines and not on the practice of how to “spread the love of God”. We are aware that “God is love and those who abide in love abide in God” (1 Jn 4:16) (FT 4). But the application of it in our life is absent.

In India we are constantly in contact with the poor. We see them in the streets, in the market places, when we travel and most of all we employ them in our homes as domestic workers, cleaners, garbage collectors, guards, drivers, etc. We meet them in our places of work, in our aided schools, and often they are part of our parish community. Do we see them as our brothers and sisters, “as a single human family, as fellow travellers sharing the same

flesh, as children of the same earth which is our common home”? (FT 8)

“The majority of Christians seem content to live secure within the parish community which provides spiritual nourishment, education and social interaction. The Catholic Church provides a secure setup for its people. The harsh reality of millions of India’s poor and marginalized do not seem to concern us. Some may indulge in armchair debates about the government and how it does nothing to eradicate poverty, about the perceived laziness of the poor to find work, etc. But we never discuss how we ourselves should get involved to change the situation” (Saldanha 2005).

“In general, the application of the Gospel message is limited to our private life and practice of faith. We leave the concerns of public life in society, politics and economics to the powers of selfishness and greed. Jesus has been reduced to a personal savior and a name to be praised—without discipleship. We have come to believe that Jesus died on the cross so that we can be comfortable in our faith. Jesus has been made irrelevant to the concerns of the world. It explains the throngs of people attending novenas, visiting shrines, going on pilgrimages etc. for personal favours” (Saldanha 2005).

In the early 1990s part-time domestic workers in my community were not aware of their rights as workers. I realised that most were Dalits, whose husbands were laid-off mill workers who sat at home drinking their wife’s earnings, while she worked part-time jobs in about four houses to make ends meet. I felt the need to reach out to them and make them aware of their rights as workers to get a living wage, a day off each week and a month’s paid leave. My work with them was largely successful, but I suffered a big back lash from my own parish community. A woman actually stopped me on the road and said to me “People of Santa Cruz want your blood.” Another said, “what do you think you are doing

upsetting the harmony of our homes by making our workers fight with us?” A third said “Why do we have to give them holidays? They are not like us!”

“It frequently becomes clear that, in practice, human rights are not equal for all.” Respect for those rights “is the preliminary condition for a country’s social and economic development. When the dignity of the human person is respected, and his or her rights recognized and guaranteed, creativity and interdependence thrive, and the creativity of the human personality is released through actions that further the common good”. (FT 22) Pope Francis brings to our attention the need for us to recognize the universality of human rights, because our workers are like us, they are all our brothers and sisters.

During the lockdown, it was widely known that most domestic workers had to depend on handouts because employers did not pay salaries to their workers. Workers languished with their families, many of them joining the exodus to their villages because they could not afford to continue to live in cities, because we failed to see them as sharing in the same anxiety, the same fears and insecurity that we were faced with. In FT 7 Pope Francis reminds us “the Covid-19 pandemic unexpectedly erupted, exposing our false securities”; “by acknowledging the dignity of each human person, we can contribute to the rebirth of a universal aspiration to fraternity” (FT 8).

Many homes have engaged live-in domestic workers. These workers are kept like slaves. The International Labour Organization calls domestic work as ‘modern day slavery’. “Equality and human dignity are the basic values underlying all human rights. There is perhaps, no greater denial of these universally shared values than treating human beings as mere chattels that can be owned, controlled, exploited and enslaved.

Yet, human beings across the world still suffer this fate.”¹ Live-in workers are at the beck and call of the family 24 x 7 with no free time, no friends, no one to talk to. They are separated from their families, taking up jobs in cities whose spaces are alien to them, some of them are young teenagers. But we only see them as ‘servants’, not as humans. “We should also recognize that “even though the international community has adopted numerous agreements aimed at ending slavery in all its forms, and has launched various strategies to combat this phenomenon, millions of people today – children, women and men of all ages – are deprived of freedom and forced to live in conditions akin to slavery...” (FT 24).

3. Women’s Rights

This encyclical reminds us “the organization of societies worldwide is still far from reflecting clearly that women possess the same dignity and identical rights as men. We say one thing with words, but our decisions and reality tell another story. Indeed, “doubly poor are those women who endure situations of exclusion, mistreatment and violence, since they are frequently less able to defend their rights” (FT 23).

Sadly, I have to point out that the Catholic Church is an institution where women do not have rights identical to men.

¹ UN Special Rapporteur Gulnara Shahinian, on Contemporary Forms of Slavery, highlights modern day domestic servitude as a global human rights concern, in her Report to the Human Rights Council in October 2010, “From domestic work to modern day slavery”, https://www.ilo.org/global/about-the-ilo/newsroom/news/WCMS_146485/lang--en/index.htm accessed 13 Oct. 2021.

Pope Francis often refers to the Church as a pyramid. Women are at the bottom of this pyramid because they have no power to participate in any decisions taken in the Church even when it concerns their own lives. The exclusion of women from leadership and decision making has made them vulnerable to exploitation and even violence.

Violence done to women in the family is hardly ever condemned in the Church. Wife beating is never named as a sin, and the practice continues with impunity even into the 21st century. Violence comes in ways other than physical beating. Women suffer from emotional, mental and economic violence as well. This violence reflects on the children who also suffer trauma with their mother, bringing instability in the home. Most women are unable to take any action because they lack social or family support. As pointed out earlier Catholic women hardly receive help from the Church. When the Commission for Women was established in the diocese and parish level, women working at these levels were encouraged to be proactive on the issue of domestic violence, but today it is not so. Thankfully we have the feminist movement active in the country with dedicated women who are always ready to help. The Church falls dismally far behind secular society.

Church agencies have projects to empower women economically through income generating skills training. But if women are not empowered to question their subordination to men which often results in violence, these projects are counter-productive in preventing violence, as women will be compelled to hand over their earnings to their drunken husbands.

4. Building Walls to Keep out the ‘Other’

FT further says: “the unknown, unfamiliar, not part of the village. It is the territory of the “barbarian”, from whom we must defend ourselves at all costs. As a result, new walls are erected for self-preservation, the outside world ceases to exist and leaves only “my” world, to the point that others, no longer considered human

beings possessed of an inalienable dignity, become only “them”. Once more, we encounter “the temptation to build a culture of walls, to raise walls, walls in the heart, walls on the land, in order to prevent this encounter with other cultures, with other people. And those who raise walls will end up as slaves within the very walls they have built. They are left without horizons, for they lack this interchange with others” (FT 27).

We build these walls in our parishes, in our families, communities, when we feel superior to the other. We do not join community events or parish activities, because we do not want to rub shoulders with those we feel are not the same as us because they come from a different economic class, or different caste, or different region. We even look down on people of other faith.

Can our catechesis tackle the divisions humans carry within them based on skin colour, economic status, profession, etc.? For when we are baptized all divisions are wiped away because we are all baptized into the one body of Christ (Gal 3:28). If we have to help bring about the reign of God amongst us, then we have to develop a mindset that does not erect walls. The forthcoming Synod on Synodality is just about that “Walking together in communion, participation and mission” with all people, even those of other faith.

When Jesus was seen speaking to the Samaritan woman (Jn 4: 4-42) his disciples were shocked because they had the same superior attitude as all Jews, who felt the Samaritans were inferior people, yet Jesus only saw her as a woman who felt troubled because of her personal life, she felt marginalized and isolated, he wanted to reach out to her bringing her God’s love. In return she was touched so deeply by her encounter with Jesus that she brought her whole village to meet Jesus. Jesus not only broke the barrier between the Jew and the Samaritan, he also helped break the

barriers in her own life she had built between herself and her community because of her troubled past.

While Pope Francis points out that “the sense of belonging to a single human family is fading, and the dream of working together for justice and peace seems an outdated utopia” (FT 30) he calls us to encounter the love of God first to enable ourselves to reach out to others to break down social, cultural and other barriers humans create between one another. This is the true mission of our Christian faith.

Today our addiction to our communication devices can also build walls around ourselves and keep us from real communication even in the family. “The ability to sit down and listen to others, typical of interpersonal encounters, is paradigmatic of the welcoming attitude shown by those who transcend narcissism and accept others, caring for them and welcoming them into their lives. The frantic pace of the modern world prevents us from listening attentively to what another person is saying. Halfway through, we interrupt him and want to contradict what he has not even finished saying. We must not lose our ability to listen” (FT 48). This applies very much to people in the family, communication between parents and young children, or between grown children and their elderly parents.

Many elderly parents are shut out of the lives of their children because they have no time, the frantic pace of their lives is an excuse to shut out elderly parents. “By isolating the elderly and leaving them in the care of others without the closeness and concern of family members, we disfigure and impoverish the family itself. We also end up depriving young people of a necessary connection to their roots and a wisdom that the young cannot achieve on their own” (FT 19).

While on the other hand, communication devices help many of us to bridge divides of space, especially during these Covid times when we were all self-isolated, we have to use them with balance. For many of us who live alone, or have families separated because of work in different cities and countries, modern communication

has been a blessing. It has helped us keep in touch, helped us build virtual communities that have sustained many who are isolated. These have been life sustaining and for many even spiritually fulfilling. I have missed this being acknowledged in the document.

5. Divisions and Walls Created by Religion, Politics and Economics

The divisions that are built in human minds and not addressed either in education or catechesis, end up being expressed by adults in their professional life, especially by political leaders and state leaders. Religion has become one of the most divisive forces in the world today when it is mixed with politics and economics, the mixture becomes potent enough to destroy human life. Politics uses religion to brainwash people into believing that those who are not one of us are against us. Walls are designed to shut out ‘the enemy other’ through indoctrination and the misuse of mass communication. “In many countries, hyperbole, extremism and polarization have become political tools” (FT 15). Tools to divide people, as there are a few who benefit from the resultant divisions and consequent oppression of sections of human persons.

Pope Francis strikes a chord of hopelessness when he states “Amid the fray of conflicting interests, where victory consists in eliminating one’s opponents, how is it possible to raise our sights to recognize our neighbours or to help those who have fallen along the way? A plan that would set great goals for the development of our entire human family nowadays sounds like madness. We are growing ever more distant from one another, while the slow and demanding march towards an increasingly united and just world is suffering a new and dramatic setback” (FT 16).

The numerous activists around the world, many of them young people who do not profess to belong to any faith are at the forefront of the Black Lives Matter Movement, the Climate Change Movement, or the Democracy movement. I see the spirit of God present and active in all these people, who, at great risk to themselves are standing up for values they believe in. Values of justice and peace. The activists in India have become the conscience of a nation whose leaders seem to have none. They rightly reject religion as a divisive force in society.

Western Christian majority countries who were former colonisers are now the largest manufacturers of arms, whose industry is thriving on the conflagration of so many low intensity conflicts around the world that has displaced millions of people. These people live in inhumane conditions in refugee camps around the world. Many try to move on by themselves becoming migrants and refugees trying to enter the richer countries in the North often illegally further becoming victims.

Pope Francis expresses deep sensitivity to the issue of migrants and refugees in our world today. He points out, “Many migrants have fled from war, persecution and natural catastrophes. Others, rightly, “are seeking opportunities for themselves and their families. They dream of a better future and they want to create the conditions for achieving it” (FT 37). “Unscrupulous traffickers, frequently linked to drug cartels or arms cartels, exploit the weakness of migrants, who too often experience violence, trafficking, psychological and physical abuse and untold sufferings on their journey”. Those who emigrate “experience separation from their place of origin, and often a cultural and religious uprooting as well. Fragmentation is also felt by the communities they leave behind, which lose their most vigorous and enterprising elements, and by families, especially when one or both of the parents migrates, leaving the children in the country of origin”. (FT 38)

While Pope Francis asserts “there is also a need to reaffirm the right not to emigrate, that is, to remain in one’s homeland” (FT

38), this can happen only when leaders have the welfare of their people at the centre of all policy. “Migrations, more than ever before, will play a pivotal role in the future of our world”.^[42] At present, however, migration is affected by the “loss of that sense of responsibility for our brothers and sisters on which every civil society is based” (FT 40). We have to think about this problem seriously so that we are able to accomplish our mission of making God’s reign of justice, peace and love a reality. To relegate its solution to political leaders will never work. We have to strengthen civil society from the grassroots so that every person finds hope and acceptance in their own home country. Politicians who emerge from our communities, our families, should make conscientious leaders. This is one way we can tackle this problem decisively.

On the other hand, we should become vigilant promoters of truth and justice when leaders neglect people at the margins.

6. Cultural Diversity

“Certain economically prosperous countries tend to be proposed as cultural models for less developed countries; instead, each of those countries should be helped to grow in its own distinct way and to develop its capacity for innovation while respecting the values of its proper culture. A shallow and pathetic desire to imitate others leads to copying and consuming in place of creating, and fosters low national self-esteem. In the affluent sectors of many poor countries, and at times in those who have recently emerged from poverty, there is a resistance to native ways of thinking and acting, and a tendency to look down on one’s own cultural identity, as if it were the sole cause of every ill” (FT 51).

One negative fallout of global communication is the growth of a monoculture where the prosperous countries are seen as

role models. It has drawn in the young people who tend to look down on their indigenous culture and way of living to blindly aspire to the western models of being without appreciating the values in their own indigenous cultures. “A land will be fruitful, and its people bear fruit and give birth to the future, only to the extent that it can foster a sense of belonging among its members, create bonds of integration between generations and different communities, and avoid all that makes us insensitive to others and leads to further alienation” (FT 52).

7. Creating Bonds of Communion and Fraternity

Pope Francis uses the example of our experience with the Covid-19 pandemic to show us how adversity can bring human beings together and tap into the goodness that is found in every person. “God continues to sow abundant seeds of goodness in our human family. The recent pandemic enabled us to recognize and appreciate once more all those around us who, in the midst of fear, responded by putting their lives on the line. We began to realize that our lives are interwoven with and sustained by ordinary people valiantly shaping the decisive events of our shared history: doctors, nurses, pharmacists, storekeepers and supermarket workers, cleaning personnel, caretakers, transport workers, men and women working to provide essential services and public safety, volunteers, priests and religious... They understood that no one is saved alone” (FT 54).

Pope Francis devotes a whole chapter in the encyclical to an in depth reflection on the parable of the Good Samaritan (Lk10:25-37) in order to emphasise the importance of human relationships. He points to the beginning of Scripture where in Gen 4: 9, God asks Cain, “where is your brother?” God calls Cain to give an account because God was aware of his crime. God goes on to tell Cain how his sin creates a great disturbance within him, but God did not wish that Cain pay for his crime with his life (Gen 4:13-15).

“In everything, do to others as you would have them do to you; for this is the law and the prophets” (Mt 7:12). This command is universal in scope, embracing everyone on the basis of our shared humanity. (FT 60). The call to fraternal love echoes throughout the New Testament: “For the whole law is summed up in a single commandment, ‘You shall love your neighbour as yourself’” (Gal 5:14). “We know that we have passed from death to life because we love one another. Whoever does not love abides in death” (1 Jn 3:14). “Those who do not love a brother or sister whom they have seen, cannot love God whom they have not seen” (1 Jn 4:20, FT 61).

Like the Levite in the parable of the Good Samaritan, we often try to ignore the problems of people, passing it off as someone else’s responsibility, or because we are busy, “caught up as we are with our own needs, the sight of a person who is suffering disturbs us. It makes us uneasy, since we have no time to waste on other people’s problems. These are symptoms of an unhealthy society. A society that seeks prosperity but turns its back on suffering” (FT 65). “The parable shows us how a community can be rebuilt by men and women who identify with the vulnerability of others, who reject the creation of a society of exclusion, and act instead as neighbours, lifting up and rehabilitating the fallen for the sake of the common good. At the same time, it warns us about the attitude of those who think only of themselves and fail to shoulder the inevitable responsibilities of life as it is” (FT 67).

We are also called upon to “direct society to the pursuit of the common good and, with this purpose in mind, to persevere in consolidating its political and social order, its fabric of relations, its human goals, “the existence of each and every individual is deeply tied to that of others: life is not

simply time that passes; life is a time for interactions” (FT 66).

Francis continues to stress the importance of relationships in the life of a Christian “Life exists where there is bonding, communion, fraternity; and life is stronger than death when it is built on true relationships and bonds of fidelity.” (FT 87) It is a known fact that good relationships are good for our health. “People involved in loving, philia-based relationships have fewer doctor visits, shorter hospital visits, have less pain, and have more positive emotions,” said Kirtly Parker Jones, MD, of the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology at University of Utah Healthcare.² “The spiritual stature of a person’s life is measured by love, which in the end remains “the criterion for the definitive decision about a human life’s worth or lack thereof” (FT 92) If humans grow up in an environment of love and caring, we are likely to have a future generation of people in leadership who bring these virtues and values to impact their work in politics, economics, science, medicine, teaching, etc. Imagine the world being impacted by people who love instead hate. We can witness a world envisioned by Isaiah 2:4 where nation will not take up sword against nation and will not train for war anymore. Where all the money spent on arms can be spent on the development of people in a world of peace. This can be the fruit of love.

8. Creating a World of Equality

A long standing inequality that has existed down the ages is gender inequality. Women denied rights that are given to men. People born as LGBTQI+ persons treated as sinners, not accepted even in their families much less in parish communities. They are condemned to live in the closet all their lives, not who God created them to be. They cannot live their truth, even though we are aware that Jesus came to give us all life, life in abundance (John 10:10).

² See <https://healthcare.utah.edu/healthfeed/postings/2017/02/relationships.php> “Seven reasons why loving relationships are good for you” accessed on 20th Oct 2021.

Handicapped persons also have been ignored, kept hidden in homes because people stare or pass unkind remarks. Wheelchair users have to be given easy access to Churches and public spaces.

In India, the poor are deprived of housing, medical care, employment, and several rights. They are condemned to live on handouts and charity. This violates their human dignity and value of self.

“Every human being has the right to live with dignity and to develop integrally; this fundamental right cannot be denied by any country. People have this right even if they are unproductive, or were born with or developed limitations. This does not detract from their great dignity as human persons, a dignity based not on circumstances but on the intrinsic worth of their being. Unless this basic principle is upheld, there will be no future either for fraternity or for the survival of humanity” (FT 97).

“As a community, we have an obligation to ensure that every person lives with dignity and has sufficient opportunities for his or her integral development.” (FT 118). In the context of mass migrations taking place today because of conflict, climate change or economic pressures, Pope Francis speaks about ‘rights without borders’. “No one, then, can remain excluded because of his or her place of birth, much less because of privileges enjoyed by others who were born in lands of greater opportunity. The limits and borders of individual states cannot stand in the way of this. As it is unacceptable that some have fewer rights by virtue of being women, it is likewise unacceptable that the mere place of one’s birth or residence should result in his or her possessing fewer opportunities for a developed and dignified life.” (FT 121) He also advises for limits to capitalism. “The right of some to free enterprise or market freedom cannot supersede the rights of peoples and the dignity of the poor, or, for that

matter, respect for the natural environment, for “if we make something our own, it is only to administer it for the good of all” (FT 122).

Employment is another important dimension of equality and dignity. In India where inequalities are so great, the majority are unskilled workers and unorganized. Many are employed in homes, housing societies, small businesses, and at the drop of a hat they are fired. “As a community, we have an obligation to ensure that every person lives with dignity and has sufficient opportunities for his or her integral development” (FT 118). “Not to share our wealth with the poor is to rob them and take away their livelihood. The riches we possess are not our own, but theirs as well”. In the words of Saint Gregory the Great, “When we provide the needy with their basic needs, we are giving them what belongs to them, not to us” (FT 119).

Getting involved in our country’s political and social activities is very much part of our Christian vocation. Pope Francis describes it as “social and political charity”. “It is an equally indispensable act of love to strive to organize and structure society so that one’s neighbour will not find himself in poverty”. It is an act of charity to assist someone suffering, but it is also an act of charity, to work to change the social conditions that caused his or her suffering” (FT 186).

9. A New Culture for a Changing World

For various reasons people move out of their home territory either voluntarily or involuntarily. Pope Francis recommends a ‘new culture, a culture of encounter’ that is “capable of transcending our differences and divisions” (FT 215 & 216). A “culture of encounter” means that we, as a people, should be passionate about meeting others, seeking points of contact, building bridges, planning a project that includes everyone. This becomes an aspiration and a style of life.” This helps people integrate into the new city or country they move into. “Ignoring the existence and rights of others will erupt in some form of violence, often when

least expected. Liberty, equality and fraternity can remain lofty ideals unless they apply to everyone” (FT 219).

A culture of ‘encounter’ helps with integration of people who are different in their faith, skin colour, caste or nationality. Today we are increasingly becoming aware of members of the LGBTQI+ community who are different and so often ignored, treated like they do not exist. “Subtle ways can be found to make others insignificant, irrelevant, of no value to society.” “A realistic and inclusive social covenant must also be a “cultural covenant”, one that respects and acknowledges the different worldviews, cultures and lifestyles that coexist in society” (FT 218).

Today when we are increasingly becoming aware of the need to care for our environment, Pope Francis recommends an ‘encounter’ with indigenous people. “Indigenous peoples, for example, are not opposed to progress, yet theirs is a different notion of progress, often more humanistic than the modern culture of developed peoples. Theirs is not a culture meant to benefit the powerful, those driven to create for themselves a kind of earthly paradise. Intolerance and lack of respect for indigenous popular cultures is a form of violence grounded in a cold and judgmental way of viewing them. No authentic, profound and enduring change is possible unless it starts from the different cultures, particularly those of the poor” (FT 220). Further, “inequality and lack of integral human development make peace impossible” (FT 235).

Pope Francis introduces the people of God to a new perspective of other faiths. Men of other faiths are quoted in the document. In FT 281 he points out that God’s love is the same for everyone regardless of their religious faith or even being atheist. He recommends that we come together on common ground to work for the common good and the poor. “Sincere and humble worship of God “bears fruit not in discrimination, hatred and violence, but in respect for the

sacredness of life, respect for the dignity and freedom of others, and loving commitment to the welfare of all” (FT 283).

Conclusion

The values of love, care and respect for every human person are embedded in every person created by God. That is the image of God we carry within ourselves. This image is distorted and even erased by greed and selfishness. Love and care are seen as virtues attributed to women only. In fact, men displaying these virtues are made fun of and ridiculed. As a result, we have developed an image of man that is affirmed as strong, macho, in control, loud and assertive. These characteristics are alien to the image of God, who sadly is depicted as ‘male’. This image has created the social structure of patriarchy which has been legitimized as a structure on which all social enterprises are constructed like the family, religious authority, politics, economics even several streams of medicine. By relegating love and care only to the realm of women, we have a world where politics, economics, religion and culture is increasingly individualistic. Businesses work for their own profit, countries spend enormous amount of their budgets on arms to protect themselves from the “enemy other”. The earth is exploited for profit, people are exploited for profit, the value of the country is based on its gross domestic product not on the welfare of its people. Religions have male heads who have forgotten and neglected the “feminist” perspectives of their faith leading our world to the mess it is in today.

The Christian faith is based on the values of the Gospel which *Fratelli-Sorelle Tutti* reflects through its pages. Jesus gave us only one commandment “Love one another.” We need to get back to the basics of our faith based on the gospel message of justice, peace and love, to make God’s reign of love a reality in our midst.

Christianity is a religion of hope. “Hope speaks to us of something deeply rooted in every human heart, independently of our circumstances and historical conditioning. Hope speaks to us of a thirst, an aspiration, a longing for a life of fulfilment, a desire

to achieve great things, things that fill our heart and lift our spirit to lofty realities like truth, goodness and beauty, justice and love... Hope is bold; it can look beyond personal convenience, the petty securities and compensations which limit our horizon, and it can open us up to grand ideals that make life more beautiful and worthwhile”. Let us continue, then, to advance along the paths of hope.” (FT 55)

Young people today are disenchanted with Christianity because of the way it is being understood and practised, they feel it does not address the issues with which they are concerned. For them human rights is the moral compass. They want to see gender equality with regard to women and LGBTQI+ persons, equality between persons of different class, caste and creed. They tap into a variety of scientific and social disciplines to endorse their sense of values, while the Church is lost in the tradition of a bygone era.

In the course of the “listening” sessions that Pope Francis has encouraged as part of the Synodal process hopefully dioceses will engage with the young to understand where they are at. *Fratelli-Sorelle Tutti* can be introduced to them and I am sure they will resonate with it. The future of the world lies in the hands of these young people!

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